

Modeling Global Inequality and Limits to Growth: Socio-Economic Polarization and Systemic Breakdown in the 21st Century

Abstract

Although both rising inequality and biophysical limits to economic growth originate within the global capitalist system and increasingly strain its stability, the interactions between these dynamics remain insufficiently understood. To address this gap, this study presents a simulation-based analysis of (i) potential distributional implications of biophysical limits to growth for different socio-economic groups and world regions, (ii) the environmental consequences of economic divergence and societal polarization under such limits, and (iii) the resulting risks for global economic stability throughout the 21st century. Using the Integrated Assessment Model MORDRED, a *Hyperimperialist Exploitation* scenario is quantified in which growing biophysical constraints trigger a persistent global economic decline disproportionately affecting poorer regions and classes, while the wealthiest maintain high consumption levels. The simulations indicate that this trajectory produces escalating inequality, catastrophic socio-economic impacts in the Global South, and fails to achieve effective climate mitigation. The findings suggest that maintaining high inequality in resource and energy use—supported by continued socio-ecological cost-shifting from richer to poorer regions—is structurally unsustainable over the medium to long term due to the global economy's dependence on cheap labor and materials from the South. As economic growth ceases to function as a mechanism of social stabilization, the system's underlying fragility becomes exposed, indicating that efforts to preserve material privileges in the Global North may ultimately precipitate a comprehensive systemic breakdown.

Keywords

Limits to growth; Integrated Assessment Modeling; climate scenarios; global environmental scenarios; inequality; North-South interdependence

1. Introduction

Since the end of World War II, the stability of the current politico-economic world order depends on economic growth (Schmelzer, 2017) given that the prospective of economic development and the associated increases in living standards and geopolitical power legitimizes the existence of persistent inequalities in power and economic wealth within and between societies (Nilsen, 2016, 2025). However, the ‘great acceleration’ (Steffen et al., 2015) resulting from the persistent growth of world economic output has also exponentially increased the pressure of the global civilization on the Earth’s resources and ecological supporting systems (IPCC, 2021, 2022; Richardson et al., 2023). Today, the world faces accelerating and complex global environmental changes in several dimensions that have put into question the sustainability of the global capitalist economic system and even of industrial civilization itself (Chandler et al., 2018; Keys et al., 2024; Moore, 2017; Rockström et al., 2009). Although economic growth until the end of the 21st century is still a standard assumption in the majority of global environmental scenarios an increasing number of scenarios has recognized that growth rates could decline in the future, either through intentional political action or because of a failure to solve the sustainability crisis (Lauer et al., 2024).

Scenarios based on the former are often labeled as ‘Degrowth’ or ‘Post-growth’ scenarios, tend to concentrate on reducing output and consumption of the Global North and imply strong convergence between world regions as well as within countries (Lauer et al., 2025). Regarding the latter possibility, the problem of dynamically interrelated biophysical limits to exponential economic growth and the dynamics of overshoot and collapse caused by delayed feedback loops were already illustrated in the Limits to Growth Report to the Club of Rome (Meadows et al., 1972). Subsequent research has not only updated and confirmed the principal results of the modeling study (Herrington, 2021; Meadows et al., 2004; Turner, 2014) but also has added greater detail and complexity to the study of biophysical constraints on economic development by focusing on specific questions such as the land, material and EROI constraints on the renewable energy transition (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2017, 2019, 2020), the relationship between energy availability and economic development (Ayres et al., 2003; Espinoza et al., 2022; García-Olivares & Ballabrera, 2012; Kümmel & Lindenberger, 2020; Nieto et al., 2020) or the ways in which climate damages can impact the economy (Bovari et al., 2018; Tsigaris & Wood, 2019) and demographic developments (Court & McIsaac, 2020).

Distributional aspects and inequalities are a central area of study for researchers concerned with intentional degrowth or post-growth transitions (Hickel, 2020; Kallis, 2019; Koch, 2015) and, given the inherent inequality produced by a capitalist system (Bouchaud & Mézard, 2000; Piketty, 2017) researchers have pointed toward framework conditions and possible policy measures to prevent a rise in social inequality in a non-growing economy (Hartley et al., 2020; Jackson & Victor, 2018, 2016). Conversely, the modeling literature concerned with biophysical limits to economic growth and the risks of an imposed degrowth of world economic output has not yet exhaustively addressed the possible distributional impacts of a stagnating or declining world economic output due to escalating environmental degradation and resource constraints. For example, in the original study by Meadows et al. (1972) and in subsequent studies building on a comparable system dynamics logic (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020) world average GDP declines but this number is not further disaggregated into different world regions or social classes. However, as repeatedly illustrated by recent historical examples such as the 2008 financial crisis, the Covid-19 pandemic or the war in Ukraine, in a global capitalist system the loss of world output due to economic, political and/or environmental shocks is not distributed

equally between different social classes and world regions (Abay et al., 2023; Behnassi & El Haiba, 2022; van Bavel & Scheffer, 2021). Rather, poorer classes and regions risks losing access to basic food and health products (e.g. Bayati et al., 2022) while the increase in wealth of the richest percentiles continues (Christensen et al., 2023).

To address this gap in the literature, in this article we conduct a quantitative scenario study to explore the conceivable distributional impacts of a prolonged stagnation and contraction of the world economy, and to analyze the social, economic and environmental impacts of rising inequality in a post-growth or post-‘business as usual’ era. Concretely, we seek to answer the following questions:

- How could key socio-economic and environmental variables on the global scale evolve during the 21st century without fundamental changes in the dominant political institutions and socio-economic structures shaping the production of and access to economic goods?
- How could limits to growth in the global capitalist economy affect economic inequality between classes and societies and the consumption levels of the poorest socio-economic groups of the world system?
- What might happen to the stability of world economic (re)production in global futures featuring strong ‘polarization and divergence’, i.e. scenarios in which rich classes and countries (‘Global North’) maintain their consumption levels at the cost of poorer classes and countries (‘Global South’)?

To this end, we use a newly developed Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) which is parametrized to fit a scenario characterized by increasing inequality once biophysical limits to world economic growth begin to manifest. We analyze the feasibility of such a scenario and discuss possible avenues for future research before concluding by highlighting the main policy implications of our findings.

2. Methods

2.1. Simulation model

To carry out the simulations, we use version 1.0.1. of MORDRED (Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development), an Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) designed to analyze global socio-economic inequality and biophysical constraints on economic growth. Built with the software Vensim, it integrates several dynamically linked parts: Population, Economy, Labor, Energy, Land and Climate (Fig. 1). MORDRED endogenizes critical variables that are often treated as exogenous (e.g., economic growth, mortality/fertility rates, climate impacts) and provides a disaggregated view on the consumption of different socio-economic groups which allows users to simulate diverse climate and energy scenarios under varying inequality conditions. MORDRED can be categorized as ecological macroeconomic model (Hardt & O’Neill, 2017) of medium complexity that combines system dynamics with monetary input-output (IO) modeling. The main data sources for the calibration of the model are the environmentally and socially extended IO tables from Exiobase3 for the year 2019 (Stadler et al., 2018), UN (2019) population data for 2020, consumption inequality data for 2014 from the GCIP database (Lahoti et al., 2016) and climate and emission related variables from the IPCC WGI (2021). A detailed description of the model, including its structure and equations, model data and raw data sources

is provided in Lauer & Llases (2025b). Thus, in the following we only shortly explain the main characteristics of the model components that are relevant for our scenario study.

- Demography

The population or demography module is divided into 20 age groups (0-4 years, 5-9 years, 10-14 years, etc., with the last group being people aged 95+), 3 world regions (center, semiperiphery, periphery) and 4 classes (Top20 (T20), Middle50 (M50), Bottom30 (B30) and Subsistence).¹ The world region 'center' comprises high-income countries according to the World Bank's country classification for 2019 (World Bank, 2025), the semiperiphery comprises upper-middle income countries and the periphery consists of countries with lower-middle and low income. In every region, the population constituting the global economy is divided into consumption deciles. Consequently, the richest two deciles constitute the Top20 class, the poorest three deciles constitute the Bottom30 class and the remaining deciles constitute the middle class. The different classes demand consumption goods and supply the labor force required to maintain and increase production. The mortality and fertility rates of the different classes depend on their per capita consumption as well as on government expenses of the respective world regions on health (in the case of mortality rates) and education (in the case of fertility rates).

- Labor

The subsegment of the population in the working age (15-64 years) constitutes the potential working force for the global economy. The total labor supply depends on the participation rate and the number of hours worked. Global temperature increases negatively affect labor supply and labor productivities (e.g. Dasgupta et al., 2021; Mora et al., 2017).

- Land

MORDRED contains information on the changing amounts of primary forest, secondary forest, economically used forest, cropland, pastures and 'other' land demanded by the agriculture and forestry sector, land used for infrastructure and land used for renewable energy generation. Conversion of forest land causes land-use change-related CO₂ emissions. Climate change impacts can affect the availability as well as the productivity of land.

- Energy

The energy module converts monetary into biophysical demand for energy and deducts the consumed fossil energy from the stock of fossil energy reserves and resources. The model very optimistically assumes complete substitutability between coal, oil and gas. While the fossil fuels used for energy generation cause greenhouse gas emissions, the fossil fuels used as material feedstock are assumed to cause zero CO₂ emissions during the simulation period. As the most easily accessible resources get extracted first, input requirements to the fossil fuel sectors increase with the amount of already extracted resources. The energy module also depicts changes in different types of final energy and in the electricity mix.

¹ In our scenario specification, the subsistence class rapidly gets integrated into the formal economy such that there is no longer a difference between the subsistence class and the Bottom30. Thus, we refrain from discussing subsistence related dynamics and evolutions in the present paper and only focus on the global capitalist economy.

- Economy

The economy has an input-output structure comprising 25 sectors that allow model users to differentiate between food, energy, industry and service related activities (Supplementary Table 1). World economic output is determined by final demand (including government and household consumption and investment) and the production of necessary intermediate products. Sectorial final demand of households depends on their per capita consumption while sectorial final demand of governments increases as a historical share of household consumption. Investments are made to adapt the capital stock to the size required to fulfill consumption demands. Using information about the energy, land and labor intensities of the sectorial economic activities and the desired sectorial outputs, the model calculates the required labor, energy and land input requirements (the latter two are further disaggregated into fossil fuels, bioenergy and different types of electricity, and into different land types). In the case of insufficient input requirements, it uses an allocation mechanism to prioritize the different demand components. The A matrix and the capital stock of different sectors (especially the food and energy sectors) can be affected by climate impacts as well as by rising energy extraction costs.

- Climate

The climate module converts different greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, HFC, PFC, SF₆) into changes in global average temperatures with respect to pre-industrial (1850) levels.

Fig. 1: Simplified representation of MORDRED, showing only the most important feedback relationships.

2.2. Scenario analysis

For the scenario analysis we selected a ‘divergence’ scenario developed in Lauer & Llases (2025a) called ‘Hyperimperialist Exploitation’ because this scenario focuses on distributional

impacts in a context of stagnating or shrinking world economic output and because the scenario storyline is coupled to a series of scenario characteristics that facilitate the scenario parametrization process.

'Hyperimperialist Exploitation' describes a scenario in which, after a period of prolonged business-as-usual economic growth, the global geopolitical, cultural and socio-economic conditions allow the upper classes of the capitalist centers (or 'Global North') to maintain their consumption despite the world economy's stagnation and subsequent degrowth. Consequently, the consumption of the remaining population declines, especially for the inhabitants of the periphery and semiperiphery. The complete storyline can be found in S1 of Supplementary Material 1 (SM1).

'Hyperimperialist Exploitation', thus, represents a scenario in which the neoliberal promise of economic growth in the Global South, which legitimizes the exploitation of cheap labor, can no longer be delivered. Consequently, in the scenario the richer classes of the world find themselves in the contradictory situation that they need to increasingly suppress the consumption of the Global South to maintain their own high consumption levels but at the same time their consumption still relies on the Global South's labor force.

To explore the storyline in MORDRED we have parametrized its key variables. The 'neoliberal promise' for the Global South is represented through desired consumption growth rates for the different classes and world regions: The growth rates of the semiperiphery and periphery are higher than in the center, and, in the absence of material restrictions, in 2100 the lower, middle and upper classes of the periphery consume like the lower, middle and upper classes of the center in 2019. The semiperiphery reaches these levels of consumption even before 2100, and in 2100 the consumption of the lower, middle and upper classes in the semiperiphery are two times as high as the consumption of the respective classes in the center in 2019. The center itself also continues to grow, consuming 4 times as much in 2100 as in 2019. Thus, in the absence of biophysical restrictions, the scenario is designed to result in a considerably richer world with slightly reduced but still significant inequalities between the Global North and South and with consistently high inequality within societies.

The input-output structure of the model, coupled with the capitalist basis of the scenario, implies that, once there are certain shocks or limitations of the required input factors that increase the costs of extraction, the total demand for goods no longer can be fulfilled, and economic output declines. The allocation rules of the model favor the consumption demands of the richest classes, reflecting the main allocation principle in a capitalist system: In the case of scarcity, the consumption demand of the richest classes are satisfied first, and of the poorest classes last. This tends to produce declines in the effective consumption of the poorest classes. Economic development in the scenario quantification reflects the historical tendency of capitalism to increase productive capacities and efficiency, resulting in significant labor and land productivity increases that are assumed to occur until the end of the 21st century. Capital productivity is optimistically assumed to increase, which can be considered an indirect material and energy efficiency improvement as less capital stock needs to be maintained and produced per unit of economic output. Regarding the energy technologies used in the scenario, we follow the original assumption of the storyline which gives a high importance to fossil fuels but also an increasing importance to renewable electricity. Changes in energy efficiency and in the electricity mix are parametrized as changes in the energy sectors of the A matrix which, during the simulation, approaches a target A matrix specifying the assumed changes in 2100.

Apart from this 'baseline' parametrization four scenario variations were constructed and simulated to test the robustness of the dynamics produced in the baseline (S5 SM1).

Table 1 provides an overview of the implementation of the scenario storyline in the model while S3 SM1 explains in more detail the parametrization of the A matrix as well as on the changing labor, land and capital intensities. SM2 contains the excel sheet used for the simulation of the baseline scenario and the scenario variations with all the relevant parameters.

Scenario variable	Implementation in MORDRED	
Life expectancy (unequal consumption, violent conflicts, environmental damages)	Endogenous development of life expectancy as a function of consumption per capita. Consumption per capita, in turn, is affected by biophysical impacts on production.	
Evolution of per capita consumption in the center <i>without</i> biophysical restrictions	Desired growth rate that results in a per capita consumption four times as high as in 2019.	$g_{Center_{T20}} = 1.7\%$ $g_{Center_{M50}} = 1.7\%$ $g_{Center_{B30}} = 1.7\%$
Evolution of per capita consumption in the semiperiphery <i>without</i> biophysical restrictions	Desired growth rate that results in a per capita consumption two times as high as in the center in 2019.	$g_{Semiperiphery_{T20}} = 2.8\%$ $g_{Semiperiphery_{M50}} = 3.2\%$ $g_{Semiperiphery_{B30}} = 3.5\%$
Evolution of per capita consumption in the periphery <i>without</i> biophysical restrictions	Desired growth rate that results in a per capita consumption as high as in the center in 2019.	$g_{Semiperiphery_{T20}} = 2.8\%$ $g_{Semiperiphery_{M50}} = 3.1\%$ $g_{Semiperiphery_{B30}} = 3.0\%$
Per capita consumption <i>with</i> biophysical restrictions to global economic output	Hierarchization of the final demand components	$I > G_{c,s,p} > C_{CT20}, C_{cM50} > C_{cB30} >$ $C_{sT20}, C_{sM50}, C_{pT20}, C_{pM50} > C_{sB30}, C_{pB30}$
Interregional and intraregional inequality	High inequality levels	Initial inequality ratios: $T20_{center}: B30_{periphery} = 46$ $T20_{center}: B30_{center} = 4$ $T20_{semiperiphery}: B30_{semiperiphery} = 7$ $T20_{periphery}: B30_{periphery} = 5$
Social policy	No transfers from governments to households to reduce inequality; no transfers from governments to governments.	$transfer_{gov \rightarrow hh} = 0$ $transfer_{gov_{center} \rightarrow gov_{semip.}} = 0$ $transfer_{gov_{center} \rightarrow gov_{perip.}} = 0$
Military policy	Military expenses are included in the government demand for public security which is aggregated into the service sector.	Expenses for the military are assumed to grow at the same rate as the government demand for services grows.
Environmental policy	Moderate environmental policies subject to the imperative of economic growth through changes in the target A matrix for 2100 and changes in the consumption vectors of households, governments and investment.	Reduction of fossil electricity by 90% and of nuclear electricity by 40%; replacement through renewables; electrification of 20% of energy inputs in key sectors and final demand; no additional recycling policies; no land conservation policies.
Mode of production	The model operates at a higher level of abstraction than models representing a specific mode of production. The representation of production is purely technical (Leontief production function), and distribution does not appear as wage payments and profit appropriation. Instead, consumption levels for different social groups are exogenously imposed according to different scenarios.	
Goal of production	Output is directed to fulfill investment (accumulation) and consumption demands of governments and household, guaranteeing the reproduction and stability of the current socio-economic system	
Allocation principle	Class as indicator of personal wealth and income is the main allocation principle of scarce goods.	

Labor productivity	Change of target sectoral labor intensities in 2100	Decrease of global sectoral labor intensities to the levels of the center (Global North) in 2019.
Capital productivity	Change of target sectoral capital intensities in 2100	Capital productivity increases by 20%.
Land intensity	Change of target land intensities in 2100	Annual increase of global land productivity by 2.25% for all land types.
Energy intensity	Energy intensity declines through improvements in economic processes and through electrification, both of which is reflected in the energy sectors of the A matrix	Reduction of input coefficients from energy sectors by 5%; 20% shift from non-electricity energy sectors to renewable electricity sectors for key economic sectors.
Energy types	Energy sectors representing different energy types: sector 3 (coal, oil, gas); 10 (biomass energy); sectors 12-20 (fossil, nuclear, hydro, wind, biomass, solar PV, solar thermal, tide and geothermal electricity).	High importance of fossil fuels, especially petroleum; increasing importance of renewable electricity.
Climate Mitigation	No particular climate mitigation goals.	
Ecosystem integrity	Ecosystem integrity declines due to land use changes (conversion of forests into agricultural land and settlements).	Low priorities for land that is not used by the economy: Land demands of the global economy are fulfilled first at the detriment of land conservation.
Sensitivity of ecosystems to anthropogenic perturbations	Low sensitivity reflected through the absence of feedback mechanisms of declining biodiversity and ecosystem integrity on economic productive capacities.	
Climate Sensitivity	Best guess for climate sensitivity in climate module.	<i>Climate Sensitivity = 3°C</i>
	Climate system feedbacks.	No feedbacks assumed in the base run (cf. S5 SM1).
Quantity of accessible materials	No restrictions on the quantity of minerals that can be extracted; assumption of perfect substitutability between different types of fossil fuels resulting in relatively high amounts of accessible resources; Exponential cost modeling of input requirements to the energy sectors with respect to total fossil resources estimated by the BGR (2020); Input requirements assumed to increase by approximately 1.5 by the time coal, oil and gas reserves are depleted, and nearly triple by the time oil and gas resources are depleted.	

Table 1: Overview of scenario parametrization in MORDRED.

3. Results

The simulation results, which cover the time period 2019 to 2105, shed light on possible changes in the evolution of key socio-economic and environmental variables on the global scale (section 3.1) and changes in intraregional and interregional inequalities (section 3.2) linked to a ‘Hyperimperialist exploitation’ scenario, as well as on the stability and ‘feasibility’ of this scenario over time (section 3.3).

3.1. Socio-economic and environmental developments on the global scale

In accordance with the scenario storyline, all socio-economic variables and most environmental variables at the global level initially follow business-as-usual trends before exhibiting historically discontinuous dynamics beginning in the second half of the 21st century.

World output (the sum of final demand and intermediate production) increases continuously from €156 trillion in 2019 to a peak of €371 trillion in 2071. From 2075 onwards, global output

declines approximately linearly to €311 trillion in 2094. As illustrated in Fig. 2, from that year onwards the decline becomes exponential, and by the end of the simulation, global output is more than five times lower than in 2019. This pattern mirrors the evolution of the world population (Fig. 2b). Starting from around 7.8 billion in 2019, the population grows moderately to 8.75 billion between 2053 and 2057 before gradually declining to its initial size by 2094. However, when global economic output collapses abruptly, population size follows suit: between 2094 and 2105, the world population decreases by 6.5 billion people. As a result of these changes, global average consumption more than doubles during the first six decades of the simulation, reaching €12,590 per year in 2071. It then declines to €9,000 in 2100, before rising again as population declines faster than output. The evolution of the global energy system under this scenario is also non-linear and discontinuous but more differentiated than that of the socio-economic variables. While total output grows by 238% during the first half of the simulation, total final energy use rises more slowly but over a longer period—from 373 EJ in 2019 to a peak of 722 EJ in 2093. Between 2094 and 2105, total final energy follows world output and population in their exponential decline. By the end of the simulation, global final energy use is 80% lower than in 2019. Taken together, these economic, demographic, and technological developments indicate a large-scale systemic breakdown of the global economy by the end of the 21st century.

The increase in energy consumption levels despite stagnating and later declining world output in the final decades of the 21st century can be explained by rising input requirements for producing economic output, driven by higher fossil fuel extraction costs and the growing impacts of climate change (cf. Fig. 4d). These factors increasingly outweigh the continuing efficiency gains within the economy.

The rising energy consumption levels compared to the stagnant and subsequently declining world economic output during the last four decades of the 21st century can be explained by increasing input requirements to produce economic output, caused by an increase in the extraction costs of fossil fuels, as well as climate change impacts (cf. Fig. 4d). These factors increasingly outweigh the continuing energy efficiency gains in the economy.

Disaggregating final energy types (Fig. 2c), reveals that the simulation reflects the storyline's emphasis on the continued dominance of fossil fuels and the rising importance of electricity. While non-electric fossil energy growth slows in the 2050s and peaks in 2082, electricity demand continues to rise despite economic stagnation and contraction, though at a slower pace than in the early 21st century. In line with the scenario parameters, the electricity mix undergoes rapid and consistent "greening" (Fig. 2d). During the high-growth phase, the expansion of renewables leads only to a slow decline in fossil electricity production—from 52 EJ in 2019 to 48 EJ in 2052. However, as biophysical limits increasingly constrain accumulation while renewable expansion continues, the decline of fossil electricity accelerates, reaching a historically low value of 0.9 EJ by 2105. Nuclear electricity almost doubles, peaking at 15.4 EJ between 2058 and 2062, before declining steadily to 7.5 EJ by 2096, a level lower than at the simulation's start.

Renewable energy sources experience persistent growth despite economic stagnation: hydroelectricity expands exponentially until the global slowdown of the 2060s, after which it stabilizes at around 55 EJ between 2075 and 2095, while wind- and solar-PV-based electricity grow continuously from about 5 EJ and 2 EJ in 2019 to 70 EJ and 68 EJ in 2094, respectively. Yet, the sharp contraction in energy demand following the systemic economic collapse at the end of the century also leads to an abrupt decline in renewable generation.

Despite the expansion of renewables and the decline in global economic production, global average temperature continues to rise, reaching 3.94 °C by 2100 (Fig. 1f). This outcome underscores the incompatibility of the quantified scenario storyline with effective climate mitigation strategies. The persistent temperature increase stems from global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Fig. 1e), which, although decreasing after 2074, remain between 80 and 100 Gt CO₂-equivalent per year—more than 1.5 times current levels. The simulations therefore demonstrate that a sustained decline in global economic output does not necessarily result in a strong reduction of emissions or a slowdown in warming. Rather, the externalities generated during the business-as-usual growth phase—such as depletion of easily accessible resources and worsening climate impacts—manifest during the economic decline phase, due to time-lagged feedbacks between economic and environmental systems (cf. Meadows et al., 1992). Consequently, by the end of the 21st century, the world finds itself in an extremely vulnerable position, trapped between a collapsing global economy and climate conditions unprecedented in human history.

Fig. 2: Evolution of world output (a) and world population (b), fossil fuels and electricity (c), electricity mix (d), GHG emissions (e) and global average temperature with respect to 1850 (f).

3.2. Limits to growth and inequality

Although biophysical constraints on economic development emerge globally and lead to declining world output in the final quarter of the 21st century, the simulation illustrates that the distributional consequences of persistent global contraction are highly unequal and mediated by nationality and class.

As shown in Fig. 3a, consumption per capita among the upper, middle, and lower classes of the world region labeled 'center' (high-income countries) begins to slow in the 2050s, reaching maximum levels of €83,000, €40,500, and €20,200 per year, respectively, in 2074. Over the following two decades, these consumption levels remain roughly constant despite the global downturn and declining world average consumption. Only during the final decade of the simulation do all classes in the center experience a sharp collapse, falling to €20,000, €9,800, and €3,300 per year, respectively.

For the 'semiperiphery' (upper-middle-income countries), the simulation produces more differentiated trends between classes (Fig. 3b). Consumption per capita of the high and middle classes grows strongly during the first five decades, peaking in the mid-2070s at €28,000 and €11,300 per year. While consumption in the center remains stable until the systemic breakdown, the upper and middle classes of the semiperiphery experience a gradual decline from 2075 onward. The contraction is even more pronounced for the poorest class, whose consumption peaks at only €5,100 in 2074 and drops to €3,290 within a decade.

The 'periphery,' encompassing lower-middle- and low-income countries, mirrors these developments (Fig. 3c). Consumption across all classes peaks in the mid-2070s and declines thereafter. Given already low initial consumption levels, these decreases imply critical reductions in living standards and life expectancy. While the richest 20% in the periphery maintain a consumption level comparable to the poorest class in the center for roughly half a century, the poorest 30% reach a maximum of only €3,000 per year, and by 2092 their consumption has fallen back to the extremely low initial values of the simulation.

Hence, the 'neoliberal promise' of globalization holds only during the first four decades of the scenario, after which the historical gains in convergence are gradually reversed. For the lower and middle classes of the periphery and the poorest in the semiperiphery, this reversal results in severe poverty. As these groups together represent more than half of the global population, the results indicate a massive rise in poverty during the final quarter of the 21st century, driven by economic contraction and divergence. In the lowest class of the periphery, poverty-induced increases in mortality become so extreme that they trigger a demographic collapse in that region (Fig. 4a-c).

The global downturn affects the semiperiphery and periphery most severely because, starting from low consumption levels, they never reach affluence before the 'turning point' of the 2070s. Consequently, even small declines in consumption have strong adverse effects on health, life expectancy, and quality of life. The only exception is the top 20% of the semiperiphery, who catch up with the poorest 30% of the center by 2030 and maintain higher consumption until the 2090s. This outcome suggests the possibility of future trajectories marked by persistent inequality within the semiperiphery and a relative erosion of the lower classes in the center compared to semiperipheral elites.

Beyond per-capita measures, inequality can also be assessed through cumulative consumption over the century (Fig. 3.d-f). The three classes of the center jointly consume €2,975 trillion between 2019 and 2105, while the semiperiphery and periphery consume €2,094 trillion and €1,750 trillion, respectively. Thus, the center appropriates 44% of all goods produced during the simulation despite representing only a small and shrinking share of the global population—13% in 2040 and 10.7% by 2080. In the final year, the richest 20% of the center alone account for 17% of cumulative global consumption, while the poorest 30% of the periphery account for only 3%.

When cumulative consumption is measured per capita (Fig. 3.g-i), the contrast is even sharper: an individual born in 2019 in the richest 20% of the center consumes €5.65 million worth of goods over an 80-year lifetime; a member of the middle class in the semiperiphery consumes €0.66 million; and a person from the poorest 30% of the periphery consumes only €150,000. Overall, the simulation is characterized by moderate convergence during the growth phase, followed by accelerating divergence during the phase of unintentional global degrowth (Fig. S1a-b, SM1).

Overall, high inter- and intraregional inequality levels are compatible with a shrinking global capitalist economy, but their social effects are more severe than under continued growth. The result is widespread absolute poverty, escalating mortality rates, and increasing instability of the global system—a dynamic further explored in the following section.

Fig. 3: Evolution of consumption per capita (€/year) for the three classes in the center (a), semiperiphery (b) and periphery (c); evolution of cumulative consumption as share of total cumulative consumption (billion €) for the three classes in the center, (d), semiperiphery (e) and periphery (f); evolution of cumulative consumption per capita (million €) for the three classes in the center (g), semiperiphery (h) and periphery (i).

3.3. Between business-as-usual and breakdown: Hyperimperialist exploitation

The scenario quantification demonstrates that the 'hyperimperialist exploitation' narrative is not a timeless configuration but a transient phase, sustainable only for a limited period.

In the baseline simulation, dynamics corresponding to this phase emerge after roughly four decades of business-as-usual (BAU) development and persist for about three decades, until 2093. Thereafter, a 'breakdown' phase begins, driven primarily by the catastrophic decline of population in non-center regions—from 4.7 to 0.6 billion in the periphery and from 2.5 to 0.3 billion in the semiperiphery between 2090 and 2100.

The BAU phase is characterized by rapid population growth in the periphery, stabilization in the semiperiphery, and decline in the center (Fig. 4a), accompanied by falling mortality rates—most pronounced in the semiperiphery and least in the center (Fig. 4c). Total deaths increase in the center due to population aging and in the other regions due to population growth (Fig. 4b). The labor-demand-to-supply ratio initially declines because labor-force growth outpaces the increase in labor demand, which is reduced by rising sectoral productivity. However, as climate impacts intensify and fossil fuel extraction costs rise, the decline in labor intensity slows, reversing the trend in the labor demand-supply ratio. Climate impacts and extraction difficulties also increase the input requirements of the food and energy sectors, reversing previous efficiency gains. Notably, these trends emerge between 2040 and 2060, several decades before global output peaks, suggesting their potential role as early-warning indicators of systemic crisis (Fig. 4d).

The subsequent 'hyperimperialist exploitation' phase is marked by stagnation, slow decline and a deterioration of additional key parameters contributing to the stabilization of the world economic system. Mortality rates rise across all regions, and efficiency gains fail to offset the growing input needs of the food and energy sectors. By suppressing consumption in the poorer classes of the semiperiphery and periphery, the upper and middle classes of the center maintain their living standards for several decades after the onset of global decline. However, this strategy undermines the very stability of the system that enables their affluence.

On one hand, the aspiration to reach center-level affluence historically has served as a stabilizing factor, motivating semiperipheral and peripheral countries to produce for the global market under unequal conditions. Consequently, once world output begins to stagnate and populations in the semiperiphery and periphery experience a stagnation or even a decline in their living standards, social and political pressure could lead to an end of the 'hyperimperialist exploitation' phase well before the 2090s. On the other hand, rising polarization within the center—between a stagnating lower class and an elite benefiting from external exploitation—could destabilize domestic politics. Importantly, the center depends structurally on the labor force of the semiperipheral and peripheral countries because its consumption levels are higher than the level it could reach by solely relying on its own labor force. Thus, once the labor force in the non-center world regions collapses due to escalating poverty-caused mortality rates, this phase of the scenario must necessarily come to an end.

This last phenomenon is shown in the model during the last years of the simulation, which constitute a 'breakdown' phase. Population in the non-center regions declines drastically as the

consumption of lower classes falls below subsistence levels. The resulting loss of labor—previously sustaining the consumption of wealthier regions—causes a dramatic worsening of the labor demand-supply ratio (Fig. 4d). Consequently, consumption in the remaining classes collapses rapidly (Fig. 3.a-c). The structural dependency of the Global North on the Global South for cheap labor leads to a sharp decline in living standards across the former, although the magnitude of the loss depends on regional labor productivity, the capacity for rapid re-regionalization, and other factors beyond the model’s scope (cf. scenario variation 4 in SM1). During the ‘breakdown’ phase of the simulation, the remaining population inhabits a nearly 4 degree warmer world characterized by widespread poverty and high inequality caused by dissolving and dysfunctional global economic structures that still rely on fossil fuels.

As the model cannot capture the destabilizing effects of rising social tensions and distribution conflicts in the world system, it likely overestimates the period of the ‘hyperimperialist exploitation’ phase. Nevertheless, it highlights the inherent instability and unsustainability of ‘polarization-and-divergence’ trajectories in a contracting world economy.

Fig. 4: Evolution of world population (a), annual deaths (b) and mortality rates (c) by region; evolution of the labor demand-supply ratio and the input-output ratios of the food sector and the fossil energy sector (d). The mortality index is calculated with the mortality rates of the age group comprising the 40- to 44-year-olds. An index value of 100 reflects the initial level of mortality in each world region.

4. Discussion

4.1. Caveats, limitations and future work

The scenario simulation presented in this article must not be regarded as a deterministic prediction of future developments but as an explorative exercise of possible dynamics of polarization under a shrinking capitalist economy and as an analysis of the long-term stability and feasibility of such dynamics. Due to some fundamental characteristics of the current global economic system, such as the unequal distribution of costs and benefits of economic development, the tendency for an increase in inequality, and the logic of the price mechanism

that excludes the poorest classes from access to consumption goods in the case of scarcity, we hold that it is probable to observe some of the tendencies explored in our scenario exercise in the future, and, as we illustrate, the potential risks and impacts for the great majority of the world population could be qualified as catastrophic.

As shown in Section 5 of SM1, alternative simulations of the same storyline—varying in the level of climate change mitigation, climate sensitivity, labor productivity, and the degree of divergence—produce dynamics similar to those presented in the previous section, although the timing and magnitude of the global system’s breakdown differ. Thus, as long as the underlying logic of the polarization and divergence scenario—namely, a strong tendency to shift the burden of unintentional economic degrowth onto poorer classes and the absence of policies to alleviate extreme poverty—is maintained, changes in key scenario variables do not fundamentally alter the overall results.

However, it is important to bear in mind that the simulated scenarios represent a certain exaggeration of the social and ecological cost-shifting from the Global North to the Global South. It is unlikely that the consumption levels of poorer classes could be suppressed to the point of endangering survival without triggering resistance dynamics that would either lead to poverty alleviation policies or to a more radical transformation of the global economic system. In fact, once its greatest legitimation – economic growth that eventually also reaches the poorest classes and regions – disappears, it can be expected that social tensions will erode the stability of the global capitalist system. This creates a huge uncertainty space whose potential content can not be discussed here.

Apart from the highly complex social and political dynamics that could unfold in a stagnating and shrinking world economy, there is also uncertainty regarding the evolution of a series of technological and biophysical variables. Assuming that our scenario parametrization of future higher labor and land productivities across sectors, and higher fossil energy extraction costs are within a plausible range, not only is the appearance of a ‘hyperimperialist exploitation’ phase a robust outcome of the scenario simulation, but also its unsustainability. Although the amount of time the ‘hyperimperialist’ phase might vary, ultimately, it causes a complete breakdown of the global system.

Consequently, the simulation results point at probable and serious risks for the poorer half of humanity as well as for the stability of the world economy, resulting from the interaction between the current distribution rules of the world economy, degrading environmental conditions and a fossil-fuel dependent energy system.

Future research could address some limitations of the present simulation study such as the exclusion of other limiting factors such as water, soil productivity or biodiversity integrity in the environmental realm. These would likely change the relatively optimistic assumptions we made in the scenario parametrization regarding land availability, land productivity and the possible rate of land use change and shed light on the role land plays in constraining economic development. Equally, future research could focus on a possible inclusion of financial or geopolitical dynamics in the simulation or reduce the uncertainties surrounding the profitability of mineral and fuel extraction. Last, another important feedback relationship that was neglected in the present study is the relationship between inequality and energy efficiency (Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020), which in our case could further reduce the duration of the ‘hyperimperialist exploitation’ phase in the simulation. However, we hold that quantitative efforts to increase the accuracy of scenario simulations featuring polarization tendencies would

need to be complemented by theoretical work applying our simulation results to questions of peace and conflict studies, sustainability transitions, North-South relationships and the study of alternative ways for societies to organize their reproduction.

4.2. Policy implications

The climate change impacts and adaptation literature has repeatedly shown that climate impacts pose a greater threat to Global South countries due to their greater vulnerability to adverse (global) environmental changes reflected in higher extreme poverty rates, weaker infrastructure, lower financial resources and higher dependence on climate-sensitive sectors (Hallegatte et al., 2016; IPCC, 2022; Thomas & Twyman, 2005). This has led to the construction of polarization scenarios such as 'Fortress World', 'Security First' or 'Slaveship Earth' (Hunt et al., 2012), which are characterized by a global upper class residing on metaphorical islands of wealth surrounded by a metaphorical ocean of misery. These scenarios are reflected in popular narratives and perceptions of the climate crisis as a distant phenomenon, which implicitly suggest that environmental degradation might deteriorate the development options and living standards of the Global South but that the population of the Global North, and especially the richest segments of those populations, although also experiencing some adverse impacts, will be able to continue their lives without major historical discontinuities (cf. Loy & Spence, 2020; Spence et al., 2012; Van Lange & Huckelba, 2021).

Our findings suggest that polarization or divergence scenarios in which the burden of adverse environmental change is systematically placed on socio-economically vulnerable populations in semiperipheral and peripheral countries are only viable during a limited period of time and in the long run undermine the conditions of their own reproduction. Because the cheap labor force of the Global South sustains the reproduction of the world economic system, which allows the upper and middle classes of the Global North – as well as the political and economic elites of the Global South – to maintain and increase their high levels of consumption, the fate of the working classes in the Global South and North cannot be separated. Our scenario study clearly shows that it is impossible for the population of high-income countries to sustain their living standards without the labor force of the Global South except in the case of extremely high labor productivity improvements. Although a fortress scenario with high inequality is still conceivable if the 'elite' with high material consumption is reduced to the wealthiest 1% or 0.1% of the world, it is highly doubtful that such a scenario would find the necessary legitimacy among the world population to be stable in the long-term.

The interesting consequence of the unequal exchange of labor and of materials (Dorninger et al., 2021; Hickel et al., 2024; Hornborg & Martínez-Alier, 2016) between center, semiperiphery and periphery in the context of biophysical limits to growth, thus, is an impossibility for rich countries to leave more vulnerable countries on their own given that a prolonged, massive cost-shifting (D'Alisa & Demaria, 2024; Martínez-Alier, 2012) of this kind drastically increases the risks of an irreversible breakdown of the world economy.

Consequently, the most relevant policy implication arising from our scenario analysis is the inadequacy of nationalist survival-of-the-fittest approaches to the global sustainability crisis. The structural interdependency characterizing the relationships between center, semiperiphery and periphery in global capitalism requires strong global cooperation to address climate change and a series of other grave environmental issues. Importantly, this cooperation is necessary not

only for mitigation efforts but also for climate change adaptation and emergency help in the face of more frequent environmental disasters.

Ultimately, it is an imperative of the wealthier and more powerful classes and countries of the world to cut down their own consumption because in the absence of a series of technological miracles of Promethean character (Georgescu-Roegen, 1986) occurring in the coming decades it seems to be the only way to prolong the life of a global economic system that disproportionately benefits these classes. Thus, we hold that a strong reduction in consumption inequalities within and between societies is to be a priority policy goal not only in potential 'degrowth' or 'ecosocialist' sustainability transitions advocated by some scholars and activists but even in an international landscape that continues to favor the development of global capitalism.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we aimed to use the IAM MORDRED to explore possible distributional impacts of a persistent contraction of the world economy due to biophysical limits to growth. Thus, we have tested the plausibility of a 'Hyperimperialist Exploitation' scenario in which richer classes in the world's centers maintain their consumption at the cost of the rest of the world. Our findings show that such a scenario produces escalating inequality and catastrophic socio-economic consequences in the Global South and is unable to deliver any substantial climate mitigation. At the same time, we find that a scenario of high inequality in the consumption of economic goods, energy and resources between socio-economic classes, coupled with an implicit ecological cost-shifting from richer to poorer classes on a global scale, is not viable in the mid- and long-term due to the world economy's structural reliance on cheap labor and resources (Moore, 2017, 2018). Thus, maintaining or increasing inequality in a period of increasing adverse environmental impacts and resource constraints drastically undermines the stability of the capitalist global economy. This also implies that political strategies exclusively aiming at maximizing material privileges of the upper- and middle-class segments in the Global North in the long-term will cause the collapse of the very system sustaining these classes. Consequently, strong global cooperation and convergence policies would not only be adequate reactions to the global socio-ecological crisis from an ethical and justice perspective but ultimately would also be in the material interests of those disproportionately benefiting from the current world system.

References

- Abay, K. A., Breisinger, C., Glauber, J., Kurdi, S., Laborde, D., & Siddig, K. (2023). The Russia-Ukraine war: Implications for global and regional food security and potential policy responses. *Global Food Security*, *36*, 100675.
- Ayres, R. U., Ayres, L. W., & Warr, B. (2003). Exergy, power and work in the US economy, 1900–1998. *Energy*, *28*(3), 219–273.
- Bayati, M., Noroozi, R., Ghanbari-Jahromi, M., & Jalali, F. S. (2022). Inequality in the distribution of Covid-19 vaccine: A systematic review. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, *21*(1), 122.
- Behnassi, M., & El Haiba, M. (2022). Implications of the Russia–Ukraine war for global food security. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *6*(6), 754–755.
- BGR. (2020). *BGR Energy Study 2019 – Data and Developments Concerning German and Global energy supplies*. Hannover.
https://www.bgr.bund.de/EN/Themen/Energie/Downloads/energiestudie_2019_en.pdf;jsessionid=ADF18B2529B3E89FC705FDF390A57BA4.internet002?__blob=publicationFile&v=6
- Bouchaud, J.-P., & Mézard, M. (2000). Wealth condensation in a simple model of economy. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications*, *282*(3–4), 536–545.
- Bovari, E., Giraud, G., & Mc Isaac, F. (2018). Coping with collapse: A stock-flow consistent monetary macrodynamics of global warming. *Ecological Economics*, *147*, 383–398.
- Capellán-Pérez, I., de Blas, I., Nieto, J., de Castro, C., Miguel, L. J., Carpintero, Ó., Mediavilla, M., Lobejón, L. F., Ferreras-Alonso, N., & Rodrigo, P. (2020). MEDEAS: a new modeling framework integrating global biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. *Energy & Environmental Science*, *13*(3), 986–1017.
- Capellán-Pérez, I., De Castro, C., & Arto, I. (2017). Assessing vulnerabilities and limits in the transition to renewable energies: Land requirements under 100% solar energy scenarios. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *77*, 760–782.
- Capellán-Pérez, I., De Castro, C., & González, L. J. M. (2019). Dynamic Energy Return on Energy Investment (EROI) and material requirements in scenarios of global transition to renewable energies. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, *26*, 100399.
- Chandler, D., Cudworth, E., & Hobden, S. (2018). Anthropocene, capitalocene and liberal cosmopolitan IR: A response to Burke et al.'s 'planet politics.' *Millennium*, *46*(2), 190–208.
- Christensen, M.-B., Hallum, C., Maitland, A., & Parrinello, Q. (2023). *Survival of the richest. How we must tax the super-rich now to fight inequality*. Oxfam International.
<https://oxfamlibrary.openrepository.com/bitstream/handle/10546/621477/bp-survival-of-the-richest-160123-en.pdf>
- Court, V., & McIsaac, F. (2020). A Representation of the World Population Dynamics for Integrated Assessment Models. *Environmental Modeling & Assessment*, *25*, 611–632.
- D'Alisa, G., & Demaria, F. (2024). Accumulation by contamination: Worldwide cost-shifting strategies of capital in waste management. *World Development*, *184*, 106725.
- Dasgupta, S., van Maanen, N., Gosling, S. N., Piontek, F., Otto, C., & Schleussner, C.-F. (2021). Effects of climate change on combined labour productivity and supply: An empirical, multi-model study. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, *5*(7), e455–e465.
- Dorning, C., Hornborg, A., Abson, D. J., Von Wehrden, H., Schaffartzik, A., Giljum, S., Engler, J.-O., Feller, R. L., Hubacek, K., & Wieland, H. (2021). Global patterns of ecologically unequal

- exchange: Implications for sustainability in the 21st century. *Ecological Economics*, 179, 106824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106824>
- Espinoza, V. S., Fontalvo, J., Martí-Herrero, J., Miguel, L. J., & Mediavilla, M. (2022). Analysis of energy future pathways for Ecuador facing the prospects of oil availability using a system dynamics model. Is degrowth inevitable? *Energy*, 259, 124963.
- García-Olivares, A., & Ballabrera, J. (2012). *The Peak of Energy and Minerals and the Economic Future*. 1–30.
- Georgescu-Roegen, N. (1986). The entropy law and the economic process in retrospect. *Eastern Economic Journal*, 12(1), 3–25.
- Hallegatte, S., Bangalore, M., Bonzanigo, L., Fay, M., Kane, T., Narloch, U., Rozenberg, J., Treguer, D., & Vogt-Schilb, A. (2016). *Shock waves: Managing the impacts of climate change on poverty*. World Bank Publications.
- Hardt, L., & O'Neill, D. W. (2017). Ecological macroeconomic models: Assessing current developments. *Ecological Economics*, 134, 198–211.
- Hartley, T., Van Den Bergh, J., & Kallis, G. (2020). Policies for equality under low or no growth: A model inspired by Piketty. *Review of Political Economy*, 32(2), 243–258.
- Herrington, G. (2021). Update to limits to growth: Comparing the World3 model with empirical data. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 25(3), 614–626.
- Hickel, J. (2020). Quantifying national responsibility for climate breakdown: An equality-based attribution approach for carbon dioxide emissions in excess of the planetary boundary. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 4(9), e399–e404.
- Hickel, J., Hanbury Lemos, M., & Barbour, F. (2024). Unequal exchange of labour in the world economy. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 6298. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49687-y>
- Hornborg, A., & Martinez-Alier, J. (2016). Ecologically unequal exchange and ecological debt. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 23(1), 328–333.
- Hunt, D. V., Lombardi, D. R., Atkinson, S., Barber, A. R., Barnes, M., Boyko, C. T., Brown, J., Bryson, J., Butler, D., & Caputo, S. (2012). Scenario archetypes: Converging rather than diverging themes. *Sustainability*, 4(4), 740–772.
- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- Jackson, T., & Victor, P. (2018). Confronting inequality in a post-growth world. *Basic Income, Factor Substitution and the Future of Work*, 11.
- Jackson, T., & Victor, P. A. (2016). Does slow growth lead to rising inequality? Some theoretical reflections and numerical simulations. *Ecological Economics*, 121, 206–219.
- Kallis, G. (2019). Capitalism, socialism, degrowth: A rejoinder. *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 30(2), 267–273.
- Keys, P. W., Badia, L., & Warriner, R. (2024). The Future in Anthropocene Science. *Earth's Future*, 12(1), e2023EF003820.
- Koch, M. (2015). Climate change, capitalism and degrowth trajectories to a global steady-state economy. *International Critical Thought*, 5(4), 439–452.
- Kümmel, R., & Lindenberger, D. (2020). Energy, entropy, constraints, and creativity in economic growth and crises. *Entropy*, 22(10), 1156.

- Lahoti, R., Jayadev, A., & Reddy, S. (2016). The global consumption and income project (GCIP): An overview. *Journal of Globalization and Development*, 7(1), 61–108.
- Lauer, A., Capellán-Pérez, I., & Wergles, N. (2025). A comparative review of de-and post-growth modeling studies. *Ecological Economics*, 227, 108383.
- Lauer, A., de Castro, C., & Carpintero, Ó. (2024). Between continuous presents and disruptive futures: Identifying the ideological backbones of Global Environmental Scenarios. *Futures*, 103460.
- Lauer, A., & Llases, L. (2025a). Business as usual on the highway to hell? Limits to growth and future world orders. *Under Review*.
- Lauer, A., & Llases, L. (2025b). *MORDRED: Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development. Model Documentation*. GitHub. <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED>
- Loy, L. S., & Spence, A. (2020). Reducing, and bridging, the psychological distance of climate change. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 67, 101388.
- Martínez-Alier, J. (2012). Social metabolism, environmental cost-shifting and valuation languages. *Towards an Integrated Paradigm in Heterodox Economics: Alternative Approaches to the Current Eco-Social Crises*, 94–110.
- Meadows, D. H., Meadows, D. L., & Randers, J. (1992). *Beyond the limits: Global collapse or a sustainable future*. Earthscan Publications Ltd.
- Meadows, D. H., Meadows, D., Randers, J., & Behrens, W. W. (1972). *The limits to growth. A report for the Club of Rome's Project on the Predicament of Mankind*. Universe Books.
- Meadows, D. H., Randers, J., & Meadows, D. (2004). *The limits to growth: The 30-year update*. Chelsea Green Publishing Company.
- Millward-Hopkins, J., Steinberger, J. K., Rao, N. D., & Oswald, Y. (2020). Providing decent living with minimum energy: A global scenario. *Global Environmental Change*, 65, 102168.
- Moore, J. (2017). The Capitalocene, Part I: on the nature and origins of our ecological crisis. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 44(3), 594–630.
- Moore, J. (2018). The Capitalocene Part II: accumulation by appropriation and the centrality of unpaid work/energy. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 45(2), 237–279.
- Mora, C., Dousset, B., Caldwell, I. R., Powell, F. E., Geronimo, R. C., Bielecki, C. R., Counsell, C. W., Dietrich, B. S., Johnston, E. T., & Louis, L. V. (2017). Global risk of deadly heat. *Nature Climate Change*, 7(7), 501–506.
- Nieto, J., Carpintero, Ó., Miguel, L. J., & de Blas, I. (2020). Macroeconomic modelling under energy constraints: Global low carbon transition scenarios. *Energy Policy*, 137, 111090.
- Nilsen, A. G. (2016). Power, resistance and development in the global South: Notes towards a critical research agenda. *International Journal of Politics, Culture, and Society*, 29, 269–287.
- Nilsen, A. G. (2025). *Emerging Powers and the Political Economy of the Southern Interregnum*. 1–24.
- Piketty, T. (2017). *Capital in the twenty-first century* (A. Goldhammer, Trans.). Harvard University Press.
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., Drüke, M., Fetzer, I., Bala, G., & von Bloh, W. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin III, F. S., Lambin, E., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2009). Planetary boundaries: Exploring the safe operating space for humanity. *Ecology and Society*, 14(2).

- Schmelzer, M. (2017). The growth paradigm: History, hegemony, and the contested making of economic growthmanship. In *Routledge Handbook of the History of Sustainability* (pp. 164–186). Routledge.
- Spence, A., Poortinga, W., & Pidgeon, N. (2012). The psychological distance of climate change. *Risk Analysis: An International Journal*, *32*(6), 957–972.
- Stadler, K., Wood, R., Bulavskaya, T., Södersten, C., Simas, M., Schmidt, S., Usubiaga, A., Acosta-Fernández, J., Kuenen, J., Bruckner, M., Giljum, S., Lutter, S., Merciai, S., Schmidt, J. H., Theurl, M. C., Plutzar, C., Kastner, T., Eisenmenger, N., Erb, K., ... Tukker, A. (2018). EXIOBASE 3: Developing a Time Series of Detailed Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output Tables. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, *22*(3), 502–515. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12715>
- Steffen, W., Broadgate, W., Deutsch, L., Gaffney, O., & Ludwig, C. (2015). The trajectory of the Anthropocene: The great acceleration. *The Anthropocene Review*, *2*(1), 81–98.
- Thomas, D. S. G., & Twyman, C. (2005). Equity and justice in climate change adaptation amongst natural-resource-dependent societies. *Global Environmental Change*, *15*(2), 115–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2004.10.001>
- Tsigaris, P., & Wood, J. (2019). The potential impacts of climate change on capital in the 21st century. *Ecological Economics*, *162*, 74–86.
- Turner, G. (2014). Is global collapse imminent? An updated comparison of the Limits to Growth with historical data. *MSSI Research Paper*, *4*, 21.
- UN DESA. (2019). *World Population Prospects 2019, Online Edition. Rev. 1. File POP/7-1: Total population (both sexes combined) by five-year age group, region, subregion and country, 1950-2100 (thousands)*.
- van Bavel, B., & Scheffer, M. (2021). Historical effects of shocks on inequality: The great leveler revisited. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, *8*(1).
- Van Lange, P. A., & Huckelba, A. L. (2021). Psychological distance: How to make climate change less abstract and closer to the self. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, *42*, 49–53.
- World Bank. (2025). *World Bank Analytical Classifications (presented in World Development Indicators)*. <https://datacatalogfiles.worldbank.org/ddh-published/0037712/DR0090754/OGHIST.xlsx>